

PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF NON-PERFORMING LOAN (NPL) RECOVERY PROCESSES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS

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In a market economy, one of the important factors of development is the satisfaction of the needs of business entities and consumers for monetary resources by commercial banks. By providing loans, commercial banks assume the risks that arise in the process of interaction with the external environment. This, in turn, is one of the biggest threats to their smooth operation.

In modern conditions, the problem of loan repayment is becoming extremely urgent, and most banks record a deterioration in the quality of the loan portfolio. Every fifth client of a commercial bank faces problems with loan repayment. This trend may lead to an increase in the number of non-performing loans in 2022-2023, and every third client may face difficulties in loan repayment. This, in turn, has serious and negative consequences for credit institutions. In such cases, one of the basic principles of lending - the principle of "repayment" - may be violated. The bank will be forced to compensate for additional costs of servicing problem loans and miss out on the projected profit.

Taking into account the above, it is necessary to emphasize that the reduction of the share of non-performing loans (NPL), the elimination of the factors of their occurrence and the improvement of the loan portfolio determine the need to improve the mechanisms for managing NPL loans in commercial banks, which is becoming one of the most pressing tasks for commercial banks today.

Non-performing loan (NPL) management is a critical area of focus for commercial banks as high NPL levels can undermine a bank's profitability, impact capital adequacy and reduce the institution's ability to issue new loans, thereby hampering economic growth (Beck et al., 2015; Louzis et al., 2012). An increase in NPLs is often caused by various factors, including economic downturns, inadequate credit assessment methods and lack of borrower monitoring, which typically requires improving effective NPL management and collection mechanisms (KPMG, 2017; Anastasiou et al., 2019). One of the main strategies to address the NPL issue is regulatory intervention. The European Central Bank (ECB, 2017) has set out comprehensive guidance on NPL management, advocating for the development of bank-specific NPL strategies

that include clear internal processes, improved loan monitoring and asset resolution mechanisms. This guidance highlights the need for adequate provisioning and the use of “bad banks” or asset management companies to isolate and resolve problem assets. Research by Baudino and Yun (2017) further supports the role of the regulatory framework, noting that effective NPL management requires regulatory clarity and alignment with banks’ internal risk practices, particularly in regions with high NPL levels. Technological advances, particularly in big data and machine learning, are becoming transformative tools in the NPL recovery process. Research by Accenture (2019) shows that predictive analytics can improve credit risk early warning systems, allowing banks to better anticipate borrower defaults and optimize recovery strategies. By analyzing data trends and borrower behavior, machine learning algorithms can identify high-risk loans at an earlier stage, allowing for timely intervention and restructuring where possible. Moreover, digital tools streamline the recovery process, reduce recovery times, and improve collection efficiency by automating communications and using artificial intelligence to improve customer engagement strategies (PwC, 2018). Operational improvements in banks are also critical to NPL management. According to Louzis et al. (2012), banks with robust loan assessment and monitoring processes tend to have lower NPL ratios. Operational strategies such as reviewing credit risk models, upgrading risk management staff, and implementing continuous loan monitoring systems help reduce the risk of default. Additionally, Anastasiou et al. (2019) discuss the importance of NPL restructuring as a proactive approach to preventing loans from becoming non-performing. This restructuring may involve adjusting loan terms, reducing interest rates, or extending repayment schedules to make loans more manageable for borrowers.

Table 1. Information on Non-performing loans of commercial banks as of March 1, 2024

Information on Non-performing loans of commercial banks as of March 1, 2024				
No				

	Iranian Saderat bank in Tashkent			

Source: Developed by the author based on cbu.uz

A significant depreciation of the domestic currency may lead to an increase in the share of non-performing loans in foreign currency. This is because borrowers on loans in foreign currency earn in the domestic currency, with the exception of export-oriented enterprises. As a result, if the exchange rate depreciates sharply, borrowers may find it difficult to repay their loans, and the share of non-performing loans in foreign currency may increase.

In summary, it can be concluded that there are multiple approaches for handling non-performing loans (NPLs), and banks should choose the most effective methods to enhance the productivity and quality of their credit portfolios. Improving not only the quality of the credit portfolio but also the bank’s financial performance, ensuring its stability, and establishing an effective system for managing NPLs remain top priorities.

Based on the topic, the following set of measures is proposed to minimize and manage the share of overdue and problem loans in commercial banks:

1. Strengthen the capacity of divisions specifically dedicated to handling NPLs.
2. Develop streamlined procedures for loan restructuring to simplify the process.
3. Organize regular initiatives aimed at improving clients’ financial literacy.
4. Conduct systematic monitoring of the economic environment, national conditions, and various macroeconomic processes.
5. Continuously monitor the financial status of borrowers both during loan disbursement and throughout the servicing period.
6. Develop and enhance a comprehensive risk management system.

In conclusion, improving the situation with NPLs involves selecting appropriate methods for managing overdue loans, making decisions that factor in the assessment of risks, and ensuring a balanced structure within the credit portfolio.

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